

MEASURING DEVICES OF DUST MEASUREMENT USING THE GRAVIMETRIC (DRAW) METHOD

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Abstract: In this study, the gravimetric (gravimetric) method is a reliable method for measuring dust pollution by passing an air sample through a filter, collecting dust particles in the filter and weighing its weight. This method is widely used in industrial and environmental monitoring. Due to its accuracy and simplicity, it has been found to be the preferred method for measuring the concentration of particulate matter in the air, particularly PM10 and PM2.5. However, the process duration, sensitive weighing equipment and filter costs were found to be the main disadvantages of this method

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Atmospheric dusting is one of the important environmental problems that has a significant impact on human health, the environment and industrial processes. Dust particles can stay in the air for a very long time and they can enter the respiratory system and pose a health risk. Therefore, the development and application of methods for accurate measurement of the level of pollution is important in environmental monitoring. One of the most reliable and widely used measuring methods is the gravimetric method.

The purpose of the research: The purpose of this thesis is to analyze the principles of measuring dustiness by gravimetric method, its advantages and disadvantages, as well as the ways of practical application of this method.

The essence of the gravimetric method

The gravimetric method is a measurement method based on the determination of dust particles by weight. In this method, a certain volume of air sample is passed through a special filter and dust particles are caught in this filter. The difference

between the initial and final masses of the filter makes it possible to determine the amount of dust in the air sample. This method is one of the most accurate methods for measuring the weight or concentration of dust in the air.

The main stages1. Filter selection: Filters that retain dust are important in gravimetric measurement. Filters are made of materials such as polyvinyl chloride (PVC), quartz, glass fibers. The selected filter is determined by the type of dust and particle size. The mass of the filters is accurately weighed before measurement.

2. Air sampling: Air sampling is taken for a certain period of time with the help of special aspiration pumps. When the air passes through the filters, the dust particles in it accumulate on the surface of the filter. Air volume is also accurately measured, as it is one of the main factors in calculating the amount of dust captured.

3. Weighing the filter: After capturing the dust particles in the air sample, the filter is again weighed on a highly sensitive scale. The difference between the weights before and after the filter gives the amount of dust in the air. This amount is usually expressed in micrograms, and to determine the amount of dust per unit volume, the particle weight is calculated relative to the volume of air passed through the filter (for example, mg/m^3).

Advantages of the gravimetric method

1. Accuracy and Reliability: The gravimetric method is highly accurate and allows measuring microgram-level changes in laboratory conditions using sensitive weighing equipment.

2. Simplicity: Gravimetric method is relatively simple and does not require great technical complexity. This method can be widely used in laboratory and field conditions.

3. Universality: It can be used to measure dust particles of different sizes. In particular, it is widely used to measure PM10, PM2.5 and smaller particles.

Disadvantages of the gravimetric method

1. Duration: The measuring process can take a long time because the dust filtering and weighing steps take a long time.

2. Sensitivity of the devices: The scale should be highly sensitive during the weighing process. Temperature, humidity and other external factors can affect the weighing results.

3. Costs: The need to use special filters and the cost of sensitive weighing equipment can be relatively high.

Fields of application of the gravimetric method

The gravimetric measurement method is widely used in various industrial and environmental monitoring fields. The following areas are important areas of application of this method:

1. Measurement of dust in the industrial environment: In particular, the gravimetric method is used to determine and standardize the level of dust in industries that generate dust, such as cement production, mining industry, chemical industry.

2. Urban and ecological monitoring: It is used to measure the level of atmospheric dust in the urban environment, to control air quality and to determine the amount of particles dangerous to health.

3. Laboratory studies: In the study of various properties of dust, the gravimetric measurement method is used to analyze the chemical composition of particles.

Innovations and directions of development

In recent years, new technological solutions have been applied to the gravimetric measurement method. For example, automated gravimetric systems allow automation of dust collection and weighing processes. Also, technologies for more accurate measurement of small dust particles are being introduced using highly sensitive nano-filters.

Summary

The methods of gravimetric measurement of dustiness have high accuracy and reliability and are widely used in the fields of industrial and environmental monitoring. Although this method is simple and reliable, there are opportunities for further development through technological innovations. Accurate measurement of dust levels remains important in environmental protection and public health.

Gravimetric measurements, characterized by their accuracy and universality, are especially useful in large industries, such as mining, cement is relevant in manufacturing and chemical industries. At the same time, the duration of the method and the need for sensitive weighing equipment are one of their main disadvantages. But despite these shortcomings, the gravimetric method remains relevant with its reliability and wide application and remains an important tool for effective assessment of atmospheric dusting.

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